

Original Article

Awareness of Breast Cancer Risk Factors and Breast Self-Examination Amongst Rural Women of Pakistan

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Abstract

Objectives: To assess the awareness of major risk factors of breast cancer and understanding and practice related to breast self-examination among rural women of Pakistan.

Methodology: 396 rural women were enrolled for this cross-sectional study from the catchment rural areas of district Gujranwala between 15th September 2022 to 30th December 2022. A self-structured and valid questionnaire was used to gather information regarding practice and knowledge related to breast self-examination (BSE) and breast cancer risk factors. In this analysis, Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20 was used to analyse the data at a 95% confidence interval.

Results: Average age of 396 rural women was 32.96 ± 11.74 years and 25.25% of females were unaware of breast cancer. Only three out of fifteen risk factors were known by 1/3 of the participant which were family history of breast cancer, obesity and lack of breastfeeding. Out of the total population, the majority (84%) had no idea about breast self-examination (BSE) whereas only 16% know about the process of BSE.

Conclusion: Most rural women were aware of breast cancer however the awareness level was low for the associated risk factors. More importantly, despite being aware of breast cancer the vast majority (84%) had no knowledge or training of BSE.

Keywords: Breast self-examination, risk factors, breast cancer.

How to cite: Raza A, Shabbir K, Qayum S, Irshad H. Awareness of Breast Cancer Risk Factors and Breast Self-Examination amongst Rural Women of Pakistan. *MedERA-Journal of CMH LMC and IOD*. 2023; 5(1): 13-18

DOI:

Introduction

Worldwide, the most common malignancy in females is breast cancer. It is the foremost cause of cancer-

associated disability and death. Breast cancer is a malignant tumour of the breast glandular tissues causes breast cancer which results from genetic modifications mostly of a cell repairing gene leading to loss of control of cell multiplication.¹ And eventually metastasizing to liver, lungs, brain and bone.² In 2020, 684,996 deaths accounted for breast cancer globally with 63% of deaths recorded in developing countries.³ In Canada a study was conducted that revealed nearly 19,000 fresh cases of breast cancer are identified each year, and about 5300 women die annually from the disease.⁴ In 2012, the international

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Submission Date: 15-04-2023

1st Revision Date: 22-05-2023

Acceptance Date: 19-07-2023

agency for Research on Cancer estimated 2,630/100,000 new cases of breast cancer are diagnosed every year among women in Africa.⁵

Breast cancer cases are rapidly increasing in Asia because lower-income and middle-income countries lack awareness and effective screening programs for breast cancer detection resulting in an increased mortality rate. Diagnosis of breast cancer at an early stage is vital for limiting the mortality rate associated with breast cancer. Early-stage detection is possible by increasing public awareness and regularly performing the screening methods. The most significant screening method to reduce the BC mortality ratio is mammography investigation, but mammography is a relatively expensive screening technique which is not possible in many underdeveloped countries.⁶ Subsequently, for early detection of disease, an alternative method for screening such as BSE is recommended. This method can detect a lump in breast in the initial stage.⁷

BSE screening bears no cost and can be performed after initial training, by the females themselves. There is a positive association between BSE practice and early breast cancer detection. Previous studies show that the majority of cases of early detection of breast tumor are self-detected.⁸ The main barrier to limiting the use of the BSE method is the lack of awareness and knowledge about procedure of BSE.⁹ Demographic environment, social and educational factors can affect the practice and awareness regarding BSE and BC risk factors. The current study was performed to address the objective to assess the practice and knowledge related to BSE and risk factors of breast cancer among rural women.

Methodology

The study participants were recruited from rural and catchment areas of the Gujranwala district between 15th September to 30 December 2022. A sample of 396 females of reproductive age was selected by

the non-probability convenient sampling technique. Prior verbal consent was obtained from the participants after describing the objective of the investigation. Females with ages <15 years and unwilling participants were excluded from the study. A self-structured questionnaire was formed for the collection tool for data. The questionnaire contained information regarding practice and knowledge of BSE and breast cancer risk factors. It had four sections: the first one was demographics characteristics, the second for awareness of breast cancer, the third for knowledge of causative factors, and the fourth for knowledge of BSE. Data was entered and analyzed through SPSS version 20.0. For quantitative variables, descriptive analysis mean and standard deviation were calculated, whereas for qualitative variable percentage and frequencies were used. P value of < 0.001 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Table 1 gives us the demographic variables of the

Table 1: Demographical characteristics of participants:

Characteristics	N (n=396)	Percentage %
Age (Mean ±S.D) years	(32.96±11.74)	
Marital status	Single	68 17.2
	Engaged	32 8.1
	Married	256 64.6
	Divorced	12 3.0
	Separated	8 2.0
	Widowed	20 5.1
Qualification	Middle	80 20.2
	Matric	76 19.2
	Intermediate	52 13.1
	Graduate	72 18.2
	Master	24 6.1
	Illiterate	52 13.1
Occupation	Primary	40 10.1
	Student	76 19.2
	Job holder	32 8.1
	Housewife	288 72.7

study participants. It showed the mean age (SD) of participants was 32.96 + 11.74. Majority of women were married (64.6%) while 17.2 % were single. Literary profile of the population revealed that most of the population (87%) was literate with varying level of qualifications ranging from middle to masters level while the remaining 13 % were completely illiterate. Their occupational status revealed overwhelming majority of females were housewives (72.7 %) while remaining were either student (19.2%) or job holders (8.1%).

Figure 1. Awareness of breast cancer amongst the women in the rural area

Figure 2. Percentage of various information sources of breast cancer

Figure 1 depicts the percentage of research participants who were aware of breast cancer. Majority of study participant had previously heard of breast cancer (74.75%) while 25.25% did not know about the term breast cancer.

The percentage of various sources of information regarding BC are illustrated in Figure 2. The awareness regarding breast cancer was mostly obtained from media (42 %), from family and friends (42%), the internet (13.5 %) and from hospitals (6.7%)

The awareness of BC associated risk factors is given in table 2. Out of fifteen known risk factors, the most well-known risk factors to the participating females were lack of breast feeding (36.4%), being overweight (34.3%), positive family history of breast cancer (33.3%), recurrence of cancer (26.3%) and use of oral contraceptive pills (21.2%). The remaining ten risk factors were known to less than 10% of the participants.

Table 2: Knowledge of risk factors of breast cancer in participants

No.	Risk factors	Number of aware participants (n=396)	Percentage (%)
1.	Lack of breast feeding	144	36.4
2.	Being overweight	136	34.3
3.	Positive family history of BC	132	33.3
4.	Recurrence of previous BC	104	26.3
5.	Use of OCP	84	21.2
6.	Sedentary lifestyle	44	11.1
7.	Chest radiation exposure < 30 yrs of age	40	10.1
8.	Menopause after age 55	32	8.1
9.	Vitamin D deficiency	28	7.1
10.	Weight gain post menopause	28	7.1
11.	Hysterectomy	28	7.1
12.	Post-menopausal use of Hormone Replacement Therapy	28	7.1
13.	Smoking	20	5.1
14.	Conception after 30 years of age	16	4
15.	Early menarche (<12 years old)	8	2

Table 3 shows the knowledge and practise of Breast Self-examination amongst the recruited females. It showed that only 16.16% (n=63) of the participants knew what BSE was and how to conduct it. Furthermore, out of these 16.6 % participants who were aware of BSE, the majority, 70% (n=44) knew how to perform steps of BSE and yet only 22 % performed it regularly (n=10). The training source for majority was doctors (54%) followed by friends, teacher or self-taught (27%, 9% and 9% respectively). Amongst the females who were aware of BSE, the questionnaire revealed the percentage of females who knew that BSE was required on monthly basis (63.63%), BSE should be done a week after menstruation ends (81.8%), it should be done by the individual herself (72.7%) and BSE is performed by manually palpating the breast (90%) rather than by inspecting it in mirror.

Table 3: Knowledge of Breast Self-examination in Participants

No.	Breast Self-Examination knowledge	Number of aware participants (Yes/No)	Percentage (%)
1.	BSE is a useful tool for early BC detection	Y=63 N=396	16
2.	Know the stepwise procedure of BSE	Y=44 N=19	11.11
3.	Regularly perform BSE	Y=10 N=34	22.7
4.	Most appropriate time if 1 week after menstruation ends	Y=36 N=8	81.8
5.	BSE is to performed by :		
	• Doctor	8	18
	• Nurse	4	9
	• Self-taught	32	72.7
		Total =44	
6.	Source of BSE training :		
	• Doctor	24	54.4
	• Friend	12	27
	• Teacher	4	9
	• Nobody	4	9
		Total = 44	

Discussion

Pakistan's population includes a greater number of female than the male population. Among all cancer in Pakistani women, breast cancer is the most prevalent cancer. Majority of our population is inhabited in rural areas where inadequate medical management services are offered. BSE is the most inexpensive among various other screening techniques and if educated accurately every woman can be enabled to perform this modest evaluation without any help of skilled personnel.

Our study recruited female participants from rural areas and amongst them, 74.75% were aware of BC. Another separate study conducted in Cameroon a country in central Africa, only 47% of participants had heard about breast cancer.¹⁰ This indicates increasing level of awareness among Pakistani rural women about breast cancer. Our study discovered that the internet is the most significant source in spreading information on breast cancer. While another study conducted in Karachi indicate that sources of information for breast cancer were family/ friends and college lectures.¹¹ However, another study conducted in Ajman UAE indicate that major sources of information were friends and healthcare personnel.¹² Our study results indicated that three BC associated risk factors which were family history of BC, obesity and no breast feeding were known by one third of the rural population, A study conducted in Karachi indicated that influence of gene (BRCA1/BRCA2), family history and hormone replacement therapy can be the most causative risk factors for breast cancer.¹³ Breast self-examination is meant for initial self-diagnosis. It can aid patients in picking early indications such as any lump in breast, inflammation, enlargement in axillary nodes and appearance of any visible changes in skins. Our study statistics indicate that knowledge of BSE was very low in rural populations as 83.84% did not know about BSE. In comparison to international studies, in a survey

performed in Iraq 90.90% of respondents had heard of breast self-examination BSE while only 48.3% of participants had practiced.¹⁴ Another study conducted in India reported that 65% of students were aware of BSE while just 11.0% practiced BSE regularly. The reason behind the low level of knowledge of BSE in rural areas are insufficient healthcare centres and healthcare providers who spread awareness of BC and its risk factors and also impart training of BSE to females of rural setup.

Conclusion

The participants knew about breast cancer. Respondents had inappropriate knowledge regarding the risk factor, most of them knew different risk factors. Knowledge and practice related to BSE was very poor. There is a serious need for awareness of BSE among the general population therefore different programs should be implemented for breast cancer awareness and breast self-examination.

Conflict of Interest: *None*

Funding disclosure: *None*

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Authors Contribution

AM: Conceptualization of study

SQ: Literature Search

JZ, AW: Statistical Analysis

HA: Data Collection and Analysis

AR: Drafting, Revision

AR: Writing of Manuscript

All authors are equally accountable for accuracy, integrity of all aspects of the research work.